

Coagulation and Electrophoretic Behaviour of Protein Dispersion in Milk on the Addition of Electrolytes

B. R. Puri and S. Parkash

The flocculation values of different electrolytes for milk have been determined at ordinary temperatures. Zinc is found to be far more effective than any other cations examined. The nature of the anion is found to be important in determining the flocculation value of a salt. The electrophoretic mobility of milk as such as well as on the addition of increasing amounts of different electrolytes has also been investigated. At small concentrations preferential adsorption of anions occurs, resulting in an increase of zeta-potential.

The protein dispersion in milk is stable by virtue of the hydration and negative charge of its micelles. The coagulation of milk therefore may be brought about either by lowering the hydration of the micelles on the addition of a water-soluble substance like ethanol or acetone or by lowering the electronegative charge on the caseinate particles by addition of electrolytes with high valence cations or by a combination of both. Milk can also be coagulated on lowering the pH value to the isoelectric point (pH 4.82) of casein, or by the action of rennet, or heat. Although fairly comprehensive studies of the coagulation of milk on the addition of ethanol¹ or by the action of rennet² and heat³ have been reported, the action of electrolytes, particularly that of 'neutral' salts, does not appear to have received sufficient attention.

Some workers⁴ have carried out electrophoretic measurements of protein dispersions in milk as well as in other media and have even succeeded in isolating colloidal protein fractions from one another on account of differences in their mobilities in an electric field. As the effect of addition of salts on this property of milk too has not received much attention, the present work has been undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

One hundred different control samples of buffalo and cow milk were examined. The electrolytes used in the coagulation studies were chlorides of lithium, sodium, potassium, and calcium; acetates of sodium, calcium, and zinc; oxalates of potassium and ammonium; sulphates of sodium and potassium; iron (II) and zinc. The electrolytes used in electrophoretic studies were chlorides of sodium, potassium, and calcium as well as

1. Mitamura, *J. Fac. Agric. Hokkaido Univ.*, 1937, 41, 97; McBain, "Colloid Science", 1960, p. 176.
2. Pyne, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1953, 72 302; Berridge, *Nature*, 1942, 149, 194.
3. Sommer and Hart, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, 40, 571, 137.
4. Mohr and Brockmann, *Milch. Forsch.*, 1931, 11, 211; Galla *et al.*, *Acad. rep. popular Romine*, 1957, 8, 287; Albery *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1948, 52, 217.

oxalates of ammonium, acetate of sodium, and sulphate of zinc. All chemicals used were of A. R. quality.

Coagulation Studies.—To 5 ml portions of milk, contained in pyrex test tubes of a standard size and 20 ml capacity, an equal volume of a known salt solution of known concentration in water was added. The tubes were closed by a clean and dry thumb and the contents shaken gently for about a minute (moving up and down for about 15 times) and then allowed to stand in a thermostat maintained at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ for 15 minutes. The lowest concentration at which turbidity appeared was noted. The pH value of the coagulum was determined soon after by using a glass electrode.

Electrophoretic Measurements.—The electrophoretic mobility was measured by the usual U-tube technique⁵ taking all the necessary precautions. The fall of potential was 10 volts/cm.

DISCUSSION

The flocculating values, expressed as minimum molecular concentrations required to cause flocculation (*i.e.* coagulation) of milk (averages of 100 samples along with the range of variations) are recorded in Table I.

No significant differences between cow's milk and buffalo's milk were noticed.

TABLE I

Flocculation values of different electrolytes and pH values of the coagulum.

Electrolyte.	Average F.V.	Range of F.V.		pH of the coagulum.
		Max.	Min.	
LiCl	> 5.000 M	..	..	6.62
NaCl	> 5.000	..	..	6.61
KCl	> 4.000	..	..	6.50
CaCl ₂	2.750	2.000 M	2.650 M	5.75
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₄	1.500	1.620	1.460	6.93
K ₂ S ₂ O ₄	> 0.700	..	..	6.90
FeSO ₄	0.580	0.605	0.545	6.60
ZnSO ₄	0.016	0.018	0.015	5.98
Na acetate	3.500	3.600	3.450	8.00
Ca "	1.750	1.780	1.680	7.40
Zn "	0.018	0.022	0.012	6.72
K oxalate	0.180	0.200	0.150	6.25
Amm. "	0.265	0.280	0.250	7.30

*F. V. denotes flocculation values.

Table I shows that the valency rule does not hold good at all and there is a distinct evidence for a lyotropic series of ions of the same valency. In fact, the values differ appreciably even in the case of electrolytes having the same cation. Sodium in sodium

5. Krzyt and Willigen, *Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 44, 22; Richardson and Palmer, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 557.

chloride, for instance, is far less effective in causing coagulation than in sodium sulphate and sodium acetate. Similarly, calcium in calcium chloride is far less effective than in calcium acetate and potassium in potassium chloride is far less powerful than in potassium oxalate or potassium sulphate.

Zinc, evidently, is far more effective than any other bivalent cation used. For instance, the flocculation value of zinc acetate is $0.018M$ as compared to $1.750M$ of calcium acetate. Similarly, the required concentration of zinc sulphate is $0.018M$ as compared to $0.580M$ of ferrous sulphate. This observation is of some significance in view of the fact that zinc has been found at various levels of purity of rennin⁶ and the opinion holds that rennin is very similar, if not identical, with zinc.

The pH values of the coagulum show fairly large variations from 5.75 to 9.25, depending on the electrolyte used.

The nature of the anion seems to be important in determining the flocculation value of a salt. The salts containing oxalate ion, for instance, are most effective (of potassium and ammonium oxalates). The fact that the addition of oxalate ions causes removal of ionic calcium is quite significant. As the amount of soluble calcium in milk, on the average, is about 50 mg./100 ml⁷, it can be shown* by simple calculations that the amount of potassium or ammonium oxalate required to precipitate it completely corresponds to $0.0062M$ only. But as the flocculating concentrations of potassium oxalate and ammonium oxalate are $0.180M$ and $0.265M$ respectively, it is very likely that before coagulation sets in, not only the soluble calcium but also colloidal calcium present as calcium caseinate phosphate is precipitated as calcium oxalate. At the same time the colloidal phosphates held in linkage with calcium caseinate will pass appreciably into solution as potassium phosphate or ammonium phosphate, as the case may be. These changes will upset considerably the 'salt balance'⁸ and consequently lower the stability of milk.

The sulphates, although far less efficient, come next to oxalates, leaving zinc sulphate alone for the reasons already stated. This again appears to be due to the possibility of precipitation of calcium as calcium sulphate. But since calcium sulphate is far more soluble than calcium oxalate, considerably greater concentrations of sulphates than those of oxalates are needed for the coagulation. Ferrous sulphate is nearly 3 times more effective than sodium sulphate although from valency considerations alone, it should have been several times more effective than sodium sulphate.

The acetates, leaving zinc acetate alone, come next. There is no possibility of precipitation of calcium in this case. Calcium acetate is seen to be more effective than sodium acetate although larger differences could be expected from valence considerations.

The chlorides seem to be least effective. The presence of such high concentrations as $4M$ or $5M$ of LiCl, NaCl, and KCl cannot cause coagulation of milk under the experimental conditions. The addition of CaCl₂ causes coagulation only when the concentration rises to

6. Rao *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1941, 10, 215.

7. Verma and Ananthakrishnan, *Indian J. Vet. Sci.*, 1940, 16, 177.

8. Sommer and Hart, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1919, 40, 137.

*As in determining the flocculation values, the milk was mixed with an equal volume of the electrolyte solution as already stated, the amount of calcium present in 500 ml milk (=250 mg.) has been taken in this calculation.

about 2.65 *M*. These observations show that the factors affecting stability of milk towards salt solutions are quite different from those affecting the stability towards rennet or heat where such high concentrations of calcium ions would have been intolerable.

In subsequent experiments only zinc sulphate, potassium oxalate, and ammonium oxalate solutions were used as precipitants.

TABLE II

Effect of diluting milk to different extents on F.V. of various electrolytes.

Water added to make the volume 100 ml.	Flocculation value. (mole/litre).		
	Ammonium oxalate.	Potassium oxalate.	Zinc sulphate.
0 ml	0.250	0.160	0.016
5	0.250	0.160	0.016
10	0.250	0.160	0.015
20	0.250	0.160	0.014
30	0.250	0.160	0.012
40	0.250	0.160	0.011
50	0.260	0.175	0.010
60	0.270	0.190	..
70	0.280	0.200	..
80	0.300	0.200	..

The effect of diluting milk on the flocculation values (F.V.) of these three electrolytes is shown in Table II. It is seen that the flocculation values of ammonium oxalate and potassium oxalate change only when milk has been diluted with an equal volume of water. The values then increase slightly showing that dilution increases the stability of milk. Dhar *et al.*⁹ also noticed a small increase in the stability of milk on dilution. But they studied only one level of dilution (1:5). The increase in dilution may be accounted for as due to a slight increase in the ionisation or activity of the casein complex.

The effect of dilution on the stability of milk towards zinc sulphate is quite different. In this case the flocculation value decreases regularly with increase in dilution beyond 5%. This confirms that the action of $ZnSO_4$ towards the stability of milk is a class by itself.

The abstraction of fat lowered the F.V. of potassium oxalate, ammonium oxalate, and zinc sulphate only slightly, whereas boiling milk under reflux produced little or no effect.

The addition of ethanol is seen to sensitise the precipitating action of all the three electrolytes (Table III) in proportion to the amount added, obviously due to increasing dehydration of the caseinate particles.

The effect of adding relatively small amounts, though in increasing order, of LiCl, NaCl, KCl, $CaCl_2$, sodium acetate, and sodium sulphate on the F.V. of zinc sulphate is shown in Table IV. It is seen that the addition of chlorides up to 0.05 *M* does not produce any change in the flocculation value of zinc sulphate. The additions beyond this

concentration, however, far from sensitising the sol, as might be expected, actually render it more stable. The addition of even calcium chloride renders the milk more stable. This increase in stability may be attributed to the adsorption of negatively charged chloride ions from the solution by caseinate particles. Addition of sodium acetate also causes an increase of about the same order. Addition of sodium sulphate produces, however, a much greater increase in the stability. This may be due not only to twice the charge carried by the anion in this case but also due to the greater adsorbability of a bivalent ion than that of a univalent ion.

TABLE III

Effect of adding ethanol to milk on its stability with different electrolytes.

EtOH added in 100 ml of milk.	Flocculation values (mole/litre)		
	Potassium oxalate.	Ammonium oxalate.	Zinc sulphate.
0 ml	0.170	0.260	0.016
5	0.155	0.245	0.015
10	0.145	0.235	0.014
15	0.135	0.220	0.013
20	0.120	0.200	0.013
25	0.110	0.100	0.013

TABLE IV

Effect of adding different amounts of various electrolytes to milk on the F.V. of zinc sulphate.

Electrolyte added to milk (mole/litre).	Flocculation values of zinc sulphate on the addition of					
	LiCl.	NaCl.	KCl.	CaCl ₂ .	NaAc.	Na ₂ SO ₄ .
0.000	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016
0.005	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016
0.010	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016
0.020	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.022
0.030	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.027
0.050	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.046
0.100	0.016	0.016	0.016	0.017	0.016	0.064
0.200	0.019	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.020	0.080
0.300	0.020	0.020	0.020	0.019	0.021	0.120

These observations clearly show that the negatively charged caseinate particles in milk can take up, to an appreciable extent, ions carrying the same charge from the solution.

Electrophoretic Measurements.—The electrophoretic mobility of caseinate particles, based on observations made on 50 samples of cow's and buffalo's milk, are recorded in Table V. It is seen that the values are of the same order as reported by Jenness and Patton¹⁰. The separation of fat lowers the value slightly.

TABLE V

Average and the range of variations of electrophoretic mobility and zeta-potential of whole and skimmed milk.

	Electrophoretic mobility (cm./sec./volt) $\times 10^{-4}$.			-ve zeta-potential (m v)		
	Average of 50 samples.	Maximum.	Minimum.	Average of 50 samples.	Maximum.	Minimum.
Whole milk	0.862	0.944	0.750	13.792	15.104	12.000
Skimmed milk	0.085	0.780	0.604	10.960	12.480	9.964

The effect of adding increasing amounts of NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, sodium acetate, ammonium oxalate, and zinc sulphate to milk is shown in Tables VIA and VIB. Mobility increases progressively on the addition of increasing amounts of each electrolyte. Considering the chlorides first, it is seen that the effect of NaCl and KCl is about the same and that the value becomes almost double when the concentration of the salt is about 0.07 *M*. It was not possible to carry out accurate measurements at higher concentrations on account of an appreciable rise of temperature as a result of increase in electrical conductance of the solution. It is interesting to note that electrophoretic mobility increases even on the addition of CaCl₂, although not to the same extent as on the addition of NaCl or KCl. This may be due to the antagonistic action of the bivalent Ca²⁺ ion. It has been shown in Table I that calcium chloride can cause coagulation of milk at a certain concentration whereas sodium chloride and potassium chloride cannot do so even at concentrations approaching saturation.

TABLE VIA

Effect of adding various amounts of different salts to milk on the electrophoretic mobility.

Salt added to milk (mole/litre).	Electrophoretic mobility (cm./sec./volt) $\times 10^{-4}$ of milk on the addition of			
	NaCl.	KCl.	CaCl ₂ .	NaAc.
0.000	0.804	0.894	0.894	0.894
0.014	1.305	1.214	1.155	1.106
0.028	1.575	1.584	1.228	1.311
0.042	1.717	1.746	1.240	1.408
0.056	1.788	1.794	1.244	1.515
0.070	1.832	1.848	1.244	1.666

These observations confirm that the negatively charged ions are preferentially adsorbed by caseinate particles. On comparing these results with those recorded in Table IV, measurement of electrophoretic mobility appears to be more useful than that of F.V. of a powerful electrolyte, like zinc sulphate, in studying the stabilising effects of salt solutions. For instance, whereas the presence of even a small concentration of sodium chloride causes an appreciable increase in the electrophoretic mobility (Table VI), the addition of a much larger concentration is needed to change the flocculation value of zinc sulphate to any noticeable extent (Table IV). Again, the electrophoretic mobility increases by about 100% when the concentration of NaCl or KCl is about 0.07 *M*, whereas even a much higher concentration of these salts can increase the F.V. of zinc sulphate by about 20 to 30% only.

TABLE VIB

Salt added to milk (mole/litre).	Electrophoretic mobility (cm./sec./volt) $\times 10^{-4}$ of milk on the addition of	
	Amn. oxalate.	ZnSO ₄ .
0.000	0.894	0.894
0.001	0.988	0.923
0.003	1.120	1.064
0.005	1.533	1.232
0.006	0.981	1.548
0.009	0.984	1.724
0.015	0.904	1.936
0.018	..	1.454
0.021	..	1.062

The addition of sodium acetate also raises the mobility though not to the same extent as on the addition of NaCl or KCl. This shows that chloride ion is preferred to acetate ion. This also explains the greater effectiveness of sodium ion in sodium acetate than in sodium chloride in causing the coagulation of milk (Table I).

The addition of ammonium oxalate provides even more interesting features. Although this electrolyte is a fairly strong precipitant (Table I), its addition in extremely small amounts to a concentration of 0.0048M in milk raises the stability of the system. When the concentration increases to 0.006M, there is, however, a fall in the mobility. Assuming that ionic calcium is present to the extent of 50 mg./100 ml of milk⁷, it can be shown by simple calculations* that at this concentration of ammonium oxalate about half of the calcium will be precipitated as calcium oxalate. It appears therefore that the effect of disturbing the 'salt balance' on the stability of milk begins to manifest when nearly half of the ionic calcium is removed from the solution phase. It is evident again that electrophoretic mobility measurement can provide highly useful information in the study of stability and coagulation of protein dispersion in milk.

The tendency of casein particle to adsorb anions to raise its electrophoretic potential is so strong that it can take up these ions even when a powerful precipitant like zinc sulphate is added in small amounts (Table VIB). The precipitating effect of zinc ion manifests soon and the mobility after an initial rise, however, falls with further increase in concentration of the electrolyte.

These investigations show clearly the important role played by anions, in more ways than one, in effecting the stability and coagulation of protein dispersion in milk. The preferential adsorption of anions of electrolytes can also explain several departures from the conventional valency rule reported earlier in this paper.

One of the authors (S.P.) is thankful to the I.C.A.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
CHANDIGARH.

Received January 30, 1962.

*Since milk was not diluted in these experiments, the amount of calcium contained in 1000 ml of milk (=500 mg.) was taken in these calculations.